

EUROPEAN POLICYBRIEF

INTRODUCTION

TOPIC: Redefining the game: Embedding gender+ in sports academic eco-system

PROJECT: SUPPORTER

DATE: 30/09/2025

Sport as a means to gender equality

Sport is more than competition; it is a powerful social force. Sport has a unique and powerful role in shaping societies. As one of the most visible and widely practiced cultural and educational arenas, it holds immense potential to advance justice, equality, and inclusion. Sports higher education institutions, in particular, are key settings for shaping future generations of coaches, educators, managers, and practitioners. Yet, they remain marked by persistent inequalities ([European Parliament 2024](#)). Gender imbalances in leadership and decision-making, in teaching and curricula design, structural barriers in career progression, and cultures that normalise different forms of violence(s) and reproduce hegemonic masculinities continue to limit the full participation and recognition of women and gender-diverse people ([UN Women & UNESCO 2023](#)). Moreover, the prevalence of gender-based violence (GBV) in both higher education and in sports environments, including harassment, abuse, and discrimination, highlights how deeply ingrained inequalities can harm individuals and undermine the integrity of sport as a whole ([UNESCO 2021](#)). Addressing these challenges is not only a matter of fairness: it is a prerequisite for unlocking the full transformative power of sport to build safe, inclusive, and equitable societies.

The European Union (EU) has long been a global leader in promoting gender equality and combating gender-based violence. Over the past three decades, the EU has steadily strengthened its commitments in gender equality in research, innovation, and higher education in the European Research Area (ERA), and through e.g. the [Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025](#) and [Horizon Europe's requirement for Gender Equality Plans \(GEPs\)](#). Importantly, the EU has expanded its focus beyond gender balance in leadership, careers, and research content to explicitly include measures against gender-based violence and a zero-tolerance for GBV in higher education and research, recognising its destructive consequences for individuals, institutions, and societies ([European Commission 2024](#)). This commitment is reinforced through alignment with international frameworks, including the [Council of Europe's Istanbul Convention](#) and the [International Labour Organization \(ILO\) Violence and Harassment Convention](#). By supporting projects such as SUPPORTER, the EU demonstrates its determination to accelerate institutional transformation in sports higher education, especially in regions where resistance to gender equality remains strong. This leadership is essential not only to safeguard athletes, staff, and students, but also to ensure that sport can live up to its potential as a driver of equality, social justice, and inclusive growth.

The SUPPORTER project has provided extensive qualitative and institutional evidence demonstrating how sports education institutions engage with gender+ equality and address GBV. The systematic literature reviews and data collected through policy analysis, institutional mapping, learning diaries, mentoring activities, Mutual Learning Workshops (MLWs) reveal several overarching themes that underpin both the challenges and enablers of transformative change. These are briefly presented below.

1. Political and policies environment

As noted in the previous SUPPORTER policy brief (SUPPORTER D4.4), the policy contexts of implementing organisations are varied and include both sports universities and sports faculties. While, prior to SUPPORTER, some sports faculties were embedded in universities that had already adopted general GEPs, the sports universities developed and adopted one from scratch, based on the minimum requirements of the EU. By the end of SUPPORTER, all implementing organisations succeeded in designing intersectional, inclusive, innovative and impactful GEPs (4I-GEPs) specific to the sport environment, with sports universities experiencing a smooth approval process by university leadership. A possible explanation is that, as sports universities, they involved their leadership teams from the very beginning, which facilitated ownership and commitment. This shows the importance of identifying stakeholders and ensuring their and leadership support (SUPPORTER D4.3).

2. Shared understanding of key concepts

The development of a GEP in the sports field requires a shared understanding of key concepts. This includes what gender equality means in practice, the intersectional forms of gendered inequalities, and the various expressions of GBV (SUPPORTER D2.1, D4.3).

During SUPPORTER, the implementing organisations' notion of gender equality expanded. Initially framed mainly as the *absence of discrimination*, it evolved into the recognition that legislation and policies stating equality do not automatically guarantee equality *de facto* (SUPPORTER D3.2, D4.3).

The initial understanding of a restricted notion of gender equality efforts limited to numerical gender balance was also challenged. Nearly all institutions introduced, or are planning to introduce, measures on gender stereotypes, support for family responsibilities (e.g. child/elder care, household management) or integrate gender into teaching, for example in pedagogical courses, measures that would not have been possible without a shared and extended understanding of gender equality (SUPPORTER D4.1, D4.2, D4.3).

Addressing the tendency to equate gender equality with women catching up, or with measures exclusively focused on women, was necessary during this project and will remain essential throughout the implementation of GEPs (SUPPORTER D4.1, D4.2, D4.3).

As noted in the first policy brief (SUPPORTER D4.4), competitive (and even recreational) sports disciplines are typically organised in binary male/female categories, justified by the rationale of ensuring fairness and safety. This binary framework creates tensions when addressing non-binary identities in the sports universities and faculties. The difficulty of operationalising gender beyond the binary is compounded in contexts where sport systems and national policies strongly promote sex-segregated categories (SUPPORTER D2.1).

Finally, regarding GBV, although all implementing organisations operate within policy frameworks recognising the broad continuum of GBV (e.g. the Istanbul Convention or the European Directive 2024/1385), some stakeholders still equated GBV mainly with physical violence and violence against women showing the need for deeper awareness-raising.

3. Understanding and operationalisation of the 4Is

This section explores how the 4Is—Intersectionality, Innovation, Inclusivity, and Impact—are understood and operationalised within sports faculties and universities through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). In more detail:

- **Intersectionality:** mainly operationalised through the collection of quantitative and qualitative data by gender, age, origin/nationality, university status, socio-economic background, and, to some extent, parental responsibilities and disability.
- **Innovation:** in many sports contexts, where gender equality actions are almost absent, the very existence of a structured GEP is innovative. Additional innovations include the development of action plans with allocation of responsibilities and monitoring indicators. The involvement of students and external stakeholders (e.g. sports federations), and the creation of GEP teams are also innovative aspects in the majority of IOs. Concrete actions such as the establishment of trust points, ombudspersons, and procedures for gender-based violence were noted as particularly innovative in their own context.
- **Inclusivity:** achieved through the involvement of the whole organisation (administrative and academic staff, students), and the development of communication strategies. These strategies combined gender-sensitive language with diversified channels to reach different audiences in a number of IOs.
- **Impact:** the adoption of GEPs specific to sports faculties and universities is promising. It signals institutional commitment through clear objectives, actions, monitoring mechanisms, and systematic (annual) reporting by leadership, thereby enhancing transparency and accountability. However, there is still a need for GEPs to focus on transformative actions.

4. Added value of SUPPORTER

- Within SUPPORTER, regular mutual learning sessions were organised as a valuable platform for implementing organisations to exchange knowledge on gender inequalities and GBV, share practices, and explore methods, tools, and actions that can be adapted to different contexts to advance progress towards gender equality (SUPPORTER D3.1, SUPPORTER D3.2).
- Training sessions based on the GEP steps strengthened the capacity of participants from implementing organisations. The inclusion of invited speakers to share practices further supported GEP preparation. Implementing parties provided positive feedback on these sessions, and several went on to organise or participate in additional trainings within their own institutions (SUPPORTER D3.1, SUPPORTER D3.2).
- EU funding was crucial in providing resources to the teams responsible for implementing the project activities and designing the GEP. While it primarily supported the core group implementing SUPPORTER, it also highlighted the need for complementary institutional mechanisms. Such mechanisms are essential to broaden faculty and staff engagement and to secure sustainable funding for GEP implementation (SUPPORTER D3.1, SUPPORTER D3.2).

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for (sport) universities, sport faculties, and sport departments

- **Strengthen institutional environment:** Use the International and European commitment towards gender equality and addressing GBV in particular using the Istanbul Convention of the Council of Europe (applicable to non-EU- member states) and the newly adopted directive 2024/1385 on violence against women that needs to be transposed into national law by 14th of June 2027.
- **Support multi-level stakeholder engagement:** Allocate time and resources to meaningfully involve all institutional actors—students, staff, leadership, and external partners (e.g. students, staff, leadership, and external partners, such as NGOs, professional associations, government agencies, funding bodies, industry partners, international organizations, and alumni networks)—in both the design and implementation of gender mainstreaming initiatives.

- **Enhance data collection and monitoring:** Assessing progress on gender equality and addressing gender-based violence requires supporting institutions to systematically collect gender-disaggregated and intersectional data, using both quantitative and qualitative methods. In the case of gender-based violence, the presence of complaints — and even a rise in them — could be understood as a positive indicator
- **Participate to the efforts of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence:** Recognise the importance of a holistic - 7Ps (prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services and partnerships) approach. Current efforts are often limited to prevention (awareness-raising campaigns and trainings) and to some extent to protection through reporting mechanisms. Support institutions to go beyond (e.g. prevalence studies, protection against retaliation or support services), using material developed in the EU Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe [UniSAFE](#) and [GenderSafe](#) projects, and by the International Olympic Committee (IOC) who has picked up the UniSAFE 7P framework.
- **Incentivise innovative practice:** Support the development and dissemination of innovative teaching, research, and management practices related to gender equality and GBV prevention in sport education institutions.
- **Use reflective tools** such as self-assessment frameworks and Learning Diaries to gather context-specific data on gender inequalities and gender-based violence, and to inform the targeted policy interventions and actions. Another good example is the existing [FISU programmes](#) such as the Healthy Campus initiative, which promotes structured self-evaluation, and leadership-focused programmes like the FISU Volunteer Leaders Academy and Student Ambassadors, where reflective practices can empower students to drive change in their own contexts.

Recommendations for the EU as a funding source

- Continue to **support efforts to raise awareness** of gender inequalities and prevalence of gender-based violence in sport with an understanding of intersectionality as structural power relation.
- **Fund** the development of **Gender Equality Plans** that are inclusive, innovative, impactful, and intersectional - customized to the unique needs of sports education institutions rather than applying uniform templates. This flexibility is critical for effective implementation in diverse institutional contexts.
- **Embed Co-Creation Methodologies and peer learning** processes into EU funding programmes (e.g., Erasmus+ Sport, Horizon Europe) to foster institutional ownership and sustained engagement with gender equality initiatives. These approaches have proven effective in driving both cultural and structural transformation.
- **Require that Monitoring and Evaluation** of the implementation and effectiveness of actions for gender equality and addressing gender-based violence are in place (e.g., in annual reporting).
- **Promote intersectional approaches:** Encourage sports and education institutions to define and integrate Gender+ dimensions (including age, ethnicity, socioeconomic background) into their strategies. Provide guidance and support on addressing intersectionality, particularly where capacities are limited.
- **Require applicants to** demonstrate that they are **committed** to provide a safe environment for staff and students through mechanisms that are addressing gender-based violence.
- Ensure dedicated **funding for research** on gender equality in sport, including the impact of separating athletes by gender, perceptions of femininity, and the prevalence of gender-based violence and effective protection measures.
- **Acknowledge the specific political, cultural, and institutional challenges faced in Central and Eastern Europe**, especially in the **sports field**, and reflect these realities in the EU policies and reports to support meaningful alignment and policymaker reflection.

Table 1. Summary of Recommendations in relation to ERA Policy Agenda 2025 - 2027

Relevant ERA Policy 2025 - 2027	Recommendations	Responsible Actor
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Strengthen institutional environment (align with Istanbul Convention, EU Directive 2024/1385)	Universities
Enhancing trust in science & stakeholder engagement	Support multi-level engagement of students, staff, leadership, and external partners	Universities
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Collect gender-disaggregated and intersectional data; monitor progress on gender equality and GBV	Universities
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Adopt zero tolerance towards GBV using the 7Ps approach; ensure safe environment mechanisms for staff and students	Universities / EU
Integrating R&I and higher education ecosystems	Incentivise innovative teaching, research, and management practices on gender equality & GBV prevention	Universities
Reforming research assessment	Use self-assessment frameworks, learning diaries, and FISU programmes to gather context-specific insights	Universities
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Support awareness-raising on gender inequalities and GBV with intersectional perspective	EU
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Fund inclusive and context-specific Gender Equality Plans; embed co-creation methodologies and peer learning in EU programmes	EU
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Require systematic monitoring and evaluation of gender equality and GBV actions, including in annual reporting	EU
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Promote intersectional approaches considering gender+, age, ethnicity, and socioeconomic background	EU
Strengthening gender equality & inclusiveness	Fund research on gender equality in sport, including athlete segregation, perceptions of femininity, and effective GBV protection measures	EU
Improving EU access to excellence	Acknowledge specific political, cultural, and institutional challenges in regions such as Central and Eastern Europe	EU

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY

SUPPORTER main outputs

- Tatsioka, Z., Ververidou, F., Strid, S., & Wuiame, N. (2025). D3.2 Report on the implementation of the capacity building scheme. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17234854>
- Ververidou, F., Tatsioka, Z., Strid, S., & Wuiame, N. (2025). D4.2 Report on the implementation of the institutional roadmaps, lessons learned and final 4I-GEPs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17234733>
- Grahn, K., Strid, S., Wuiame, N., Lundwal, S., & Ververido, F. (2025). D4.3 Guidelines and recommendations for implementing 4I-GEPs in sports education and organisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17233103>
- Ververidou, F., Tatsioka, Z., Vilarchao, E., Strid, S., & Ipolyi, I. (2024). D4.1 Report on the design of the institutional roadmaps. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11109192>
- Vilarchao, E., Ververidou, F., Tatsioka, Z., Lundvall, S., Zaharis, N., Strid, S., & Ipolyi, I. (2024). D3.1 SUPPORTER Capacity Building Scheme. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604194>

In line with the SUPPORTER's commitment to Open Science (incl. Open Data), all project outputs are made available at the SUPPORTER community on the [Zenodo repository](#) following their submission to the EC.

RESEARCH PARAMETERS

The SUPPORTER project (SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans) directly addresses Horizon Europe objectives by promoting inclusive, gender-equal institutions and tackling gender-based violence (GBV) in key societal sectors. Aligned with the European Research Area's (ERA) commitment to gender mainstreaming and the Horizon Europe Gender Equality Strategy, SUPPORTER demonstrates how sports institutions can integrate gender considerations into both their formal structures and internal cultures. The project places particular emphasis on GBV prevention, lasting institutional change, and empowering actors at all levels—from leadership to staff.

SUPPORTER supports sport-oriented higher education from Central and Eastern Europe institutions in designing and implementing intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEPs). These plans are tailored to the specific context of sports institutions and explicitly address gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

Drawing on cutting-edge research and the expertise of leading gender equality organizations (ESF, UGOT, SEERC) SUPPORTER develops a comprehensive programme to build institutional capacity and support the creation and implementation of 4I-GEPs. The project employs inclusive, innovative, and participatory approaches to foster progress on two complementary levels:

- **Horizontally**, by strengthening institutional culture and capacity through diversity and inclusion initiatives, enhancing the visibility, attractiveness, inclusiveness, and research excellence of sports institutions.
- **Vertically**, by driving deep, sustainable institutional change to address systemic inequalities, particularly gender-based violence, and advancing gender equality objectives in line with ERA priorities.

To achieve its objectives, SUPPORTER follows a partnership-inspired model based on **three interlinked processes -analysis, reflection, and implementation-** combined with mutual learning and co-creation activities. This approach actively engages diverse stakeholders and leverages existing tools and experiences from prior projects.

Initially involving eight partner institutions, SUPPORTER aims to create a domino effect across the sports and academic ecosystem, promoting long-term systemic change in line with the [Ljubljana Declaration](#) and contributing to broader societal transformation.

PROJECT IDENTITY

PROJECT NAME	SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans (SUPPORTER)
COORDINATOR	Despoina Natsi, European Science Foundation, Strasbourg, France, dnatsi@esf.org
CONSORTIUM	European Science Foundation – ESF Strasbourg, France Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport – GSTUPES Tbilisi Georgia Göteborgs universitet – UGOT – Gothenburg, Sweden

Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas – LSU –Kaunas, Lithuania
Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski – NSA – Sofia, Bulgaria
South-East European Research Centre – SEERC – Thessaloniki, Greece
Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci – UNIBL – Banja Luka, Bosnia & Herzegovina
Univerzita Karlova – CU – Prague, Czechia
Univerza v Ljubljani – UL –Ljubliana, Slovenia
Institutul de Educația Fizică și Sport (IEFS) – Chisinau, Moldova
Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara – UVT – Timisoara, Romania

**FUNDING
SCHEME**

Horizon Europe Framework Programme, European Research Area (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01), Support to the implementation of inclusive gender equality plans (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-81)

DURATION

April 2023 – September 2025 (30 months)

BUDGET

EU contribution: 1,075,092.50 €

WEBSITE

<https://www.supporter-project.eu/>

**FOR MORE
INFORMATION**

Despoina Natsi dnatsi@esf.org (ESF – project coordinator)

**FURTHER
READING**

Vilarchao, E., Ipolyi, I., & SUPPORTER Consortium. (2024). D4.4 Policy Brief 1: support to the implementation of inclusive Gender Equality Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11402277>
SUPPORTER consortium (2025). Recommendations for universities and faculties of sport to advance gender equality and safeguard students' and staff's wellbeing through inclusive gender equality plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15575149>
SUPPORTER consortium (2025). Promoting gender equality, inclusivity, and safety in sports: Guidelines for coaches. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15780723>
SUPPORTER consortium. (2025). Promoting gender equality, inclusivity, and safety in sports: Guidelines for sports organisations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761472>
SUPPORTER consortium. (2025). Recommendations for teachers and lecturers in universities of sport and faculties of sport to advance gender equality. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16761043>

**Funded by
the European Union**

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